

ABU RAYKHAN BERUNI'S VIEWS ON EDUCATION

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The article mentions the views of our great compatriot, encyclopedist Abu Raikhan Beruni on ethics and education. His legacy has been studied the most, and it is mentioned that it is an important source in the organization of youth education and teaching science in Uzbekistan today.

Keywords: Beruni, education, ethics, education, philosophy of education.

В статье упоминаются взгляды нашего великого соотечественника, учёного Абу Райхана Беруни на этику и образование. Его наследие изучено больше всего, и помнят, что он является важным источником в организации образования молодежи и преподавании образования в современном Узбекистане.

Ключевые слова: Беруни, образование, этика, образование, философия образования.

Мақолада буюк ватандошимиз, қомусий олим Абу Райхон Берунийнинг ахлоқ ва тарбияга доир қарашлари тилга олинган. Унинг мероси энг кўп ўрганган бўлиб, бугунги Ўзбекистонда ёшлар тарбиясини ташкил этишда ва тарбия фанини ўқитишда муҳим манба эканлиги эслатилган.

Калит сўзлар: Беруний, тарбия, ахлоқ, таълим, тарбия фалсафаси.

Together with upbringing and education, it is considered to be the foundation of human practical activity. Education was considered relevant at all stages of human history. In their time, active and pure-minded people understood education as a necessary factor in the formation of goodness for a person.

Abu Rayhan Beruni, another great encyclopedic scholar of education or good morals, a prominent rock in the ocean of medieval science (as defined by the German scientist E. Zahau) and an unparalleled star in the sky of science, Abu Rayhan Beruni, left immortal thoughts and conclusions.

A person familiar with his legacy of education and upbringing is equal to him. He is considered a non-existent pedagogue, and his philosophical heritage surprised the philosophers of his time. Anyone familiar with his contributions to physics, mineralogy, ethnography, aesthetics, and mathematics cannot fail to appreciate him highly.

For example, Beruni gave instructive ideas about family education. Father and mother are not only the pillars of the family, but also each other's closest assistants. They are two pillars of child education, advisors and executors of each other in all matters. Touching on the education of women, in his eyes, a woman is educated, brave, that is, one who overcomes difficulties with her husband, shameless, takes her husband on her head, cares about the upbringing of children, should not be oppressed and ignorant, possessing modesty and insight, a faithful helper to her husband, a home - he wrote that he is a person who does

household chores well, who cleans himself, his clothes, and his place of residence. In his famous work on mineralogy, he gave the useful advice given by fathers to their daughters who are getting married. According to the scientist, if the family environment is beautiful during the mother's pregnancy, the child will be born beautiful. For the birth of a healthy child, the health of the parents is filled with the beauty of the environment. According to Beruni, too much advice is a vice, in its place, and enough is curative. Constantly making your husband jealous is the key to separation, and holding a grudge breeds hatred. It is better to always be friendly with the husband than any magic. Constant cleansing with water is the first of the auspicious things. It is better if a person who is free from flaws and defects gives advice. Such a person can help others to overcome their shortcomings.

The great scientist also had deep knowledge of psychology. He says that it is better to always keep the child's morals in a moderate state. For this, it is necessary to protect the child from fear, anger, sadness, insomnia. Children should be helped to find harmless things and play with useful toys. "Iron discipline" is also harmful to a child. More explanation, clarifying what's good and what's bad would work. As a result, the child becomes well-behaved. Sometimes bad behavior and habits can be formed in a child from customer disorders.

An unhealthy family environment affects other families. Because when children from different households go out, vices and bad morals pass from one to the other. When bad behavior becomes a habit, it causes the client to break down. Beruni emphasizes that anger inflames the nerves, sadness weakens a person, and indecision paralyzes emotional energy. Due to moderation of behavior, human organs become healthy.

Beruni's conclusions about education were very important for his time. We have the right to call him a great pedagogue, a connoisseur of the science of education. According to Beruni, a happy family is dominated by proper upbringing. Also, those women should not be slaves to jewelry, but should have a moral image. Outer beauty is fleeting, and inner beauty keeps a person in a state of greatness. The key to family happiness is proper education for all members. Beruni emphasizes that the role of halal and haram is important in education.

He also talks about cleanliness and purity, saying that in addition to a person's external appearance, cleanliness of clothes, cleanliness of the body, it is necessary to have a clean inner world, moral-spiritual image and conscientiousness: "the polar peak of praise is kindness, and the basis of kindness is cleanliness and purity." concludes.

Beruni also gave valuable insights about truthfulness and lying. Speaking the truth is one of the highest levels of moral quality. Lying is nothing but a bottom. In this field, scientists themselves should be an example. Beruni proudly recognizes people who are truthful, speak the truth, speak the right words, and have a clean language. Both the one who laughs at a lie and the one who tells lies deserve only hatred, says Beruni. In India, Beruni also cites the story of his childhood friend, a liar named Omonullah, whose name he deletes in later editions of the book. To those who asked him the reason for this, he replied that "the name of liars does not deserve to be mentioned in the book."¹

Beruni was against the use of lies in education, public administration, and public administration. He divided liars into different categories: unwitting liars; liars who know what they are saying is a lie; those who use lies to look good to others; those who use lies to advance their careers; those who use flattery and lies to gain wealth; users to pretend to be

¹ Бeруний А.Р. Танланган асарлар. Т.1. – Тошкент: Фан, 1965. – 516 б.

close to someone; those who seek to avoid responsibility for their crime by using lies; those who use lies to create conflict between people. These people are great blunderers.

It is said in the hadiths, "A liar is not my ummah." Lying turns away from justice, and the one who bears false witness sinks into grievous sin. Betrayer shows good behavior to people. In both worlds one should be restrained. He who has tasted the sweetness of honesty, praises the liar himself. He urges people not to bow down to what is right and true, even in front of their enemies, and to stay on the side of truth. Beruni tells us not to be afraid of his power in speaking the truth even in front of kings. The king only rules over your body, but you yourself rule over your conscience. Your conscience is clear and your heart is calm before the truth. Peace and justice, human dignity and the happiness of two worlds are important. These qualities are the qualities of a true scientist.

Beruni wrote in the last days of his life: "I had to live long for my only wish, to finish the unfinished works in my hands and copy those that I could not copy." According to him, it is good to be proud of the thinkers of the past, but it is not good for a person not to learn knowledge and not to improve spiritually. "Whoever is proud of his past generations, those generations are alive, but he himself is dead... if a person does not raise himself to the heights, the bones of the great ones cannot be a reason for him to be proud"².

Foreign education and vocational training gave positive ratings to family focus and negative ratings to neglect. Happiness is earned by hard work. An inactive and lazy person can never be happy. A prosperous country is a country where craft and its succession flourish.

² Бируни А.Р. Собрание сведений для познания драгоценностей: Минералогия. – Москва: Издательство Академии Наук СССР, 1963. – 524 с.

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